

The Implementation of Collocation in Promoting Tourist Destinations in Tour Website

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ABSTRACT: *In building coherent texts, the use of lexical items that collocate each other is one of the effective strategies. Any two or more lexical items that have a similar pattern of collocation inform the reader that they occur in a similar context. However, the use of collocation patterns in the tour websites is limited and sometimes fails to build a better context or fails to give a better explanation about destinations offered. This study exemplifies the implementation of collocation in the tour websites developed by non-native English speakers in promoting the services they provide through the website. The data were 41 tour package texts. They were analyzed descriptively by using the concept of collocation by Halliday and Hasan. The result of the analysis shows that some descriptions of destinations are built up out of lexical chains, but others are not. The lexical chains succeed in giving information regarding tourist destinations.*

KEYWORDS - Bali, collocation, tourist destinations, website texts

I. INTRODUCTION

Bali is well known as a tourist destination. Many aspects of Bali are interesting to explore in the case of tourism. The beauty of nature and also the culture is the most interesting thing if we talk about Bali. This tourism sector is the sector that contributes most to the income of Bali [1]. The development of Bali is mostly influenced by this tourism sector. This makes the existence of freelance travel agents increase.

The freelance travel agents, well known as freelancers, build their business by developing their brand through a website. However, they keep promoting their services in two ways, by website and brochure, rather than through website only. Both website and brochure utilize language to inform the products or services offered. A way used to capture attention and inform the products or services offered is by utilizing imperative [2]. On the other hand, this study utilizes collocation to build up lexical relations in promoting tourist destinations on the website.

Maintaining coherence in English is not easy. This problem is not only faced by copy-writers, students, non-native speakers, but also almost most people face this problem. As a student, maintaining coherence in English is one of the problems faced. For example in Indonesia, the students of the English Department of UIN Alauddin Makassar faced difficulties in maintaining coherence in their writings [3]. Linda in her research found the same case, the undergraduate students also faced difficulties in maintaining coherence. Besides, she also suggested that the students have to master using cohesive devices, especially conjunction. The types of conjunction that she wants the students to master are comparative, temporal, and consequential conjunction [4] due to conjunction plays important role in maintaining the coherence of a text, and it can give a positive impression to the readers [5]. The reason is simple, the conjunction connects a clause with another clause to maintain the coherence. The problem in maintaining the coherence among parts of the language used to build up a text is also faced by Iranian intermediate EFL learners. Mohseni and Samadian revealed that the EFL learners were faced the same problem [6]. The problem is also faced in the translation of a text into English. The translation shifts may happen, and maintaining coherence is also important in translation [7].

Although it is difficult to maintain coherence in a text, there is always a device that can be easily used to keep the coherence. The application of repetition is the way. Many researchers found that repetition is used in many aspects of language to maintain the coherence of a text. For example, repetition is mostly used in speeches [8], research articles [9], news article [10]–[12], women's article by native and non-native English speakers

[13], and the backgrounds of thesis [14]. However, the use of only one cohesive device to build up a text can indicate the quality of a text. The text that is built up by one cohesive device will be the worst [15].

Building a coherent text can be through grammatical cohesion and lexical cohesion. Utilizing grammatical cohesion makes a text coherent grammatically, whereas utilizing lexical cohesion makes a text coherent lexically. The focus of this study is to describe the coherence between parts of a text lexically, especially in the case of collocation.

Utilizing collocation can help the reader mapping the information expressed in the text. Cerban explained that there are three types of collocation based on the systemic functional framework. They are ordered set collocation, activity-related collocation, and elaborative collocation [16]. These types of collocation become the base to classify the types of collocation used in the text of the tour package offered on the website.

The first type is ordered set collocation that deals with collocation relating to the category including members of ordered sets of lexical items. Another type of collocation is activity-related collocation that deals with an association between items explaining something and the act (process). The last type is elaborative collocation that deals with pairs whose relation is impossible to determine [16]. This study focuses on the types of collocation applied in the website text to maintain the coherence among lexical items used by the writer of the text.

II. METHOD

The data source of this study was a website named ganggabali.com. The website is a tour website. The website consists of four main contents. They are information about Bali destinations, tour packages, tour memories, and car rental. In this study, the data used were the contents of tour packages. The data were taken from 41 tour package texts.

This study belongs to descriptive-qualitative and quantitative research. In collecting the data, the website developer extracted the texts into *.txt. The purpose is to make the process of collecting data easier. The data were collected by using the Antconc program. All the data were opened by using the program, and the related data were quoted to support the analysis.

The data that have been collected were analyzed through the concept of collocation by Halliday and Hasan. They state that the effects of collocation are not limited to pairs of the word [17]. In analyzing the data, the distributional method was employed. To support the analysis, the data that have been quoted were analyzed based on the phenomenon that happened. The result of the analysis was presented descriptively to show the phenomenon of the implementation of collocation in promoting tourist destinations. There were some diagrams and tables used to give the general result of the discussion.

III. RESULT

This analysis shows an interesting pattern of collocation applied in the texts of tour package offered through the website ganggabali.com. The patterns are made in diagrams to show general patterns applied in maintaining the coherence between the lexical items. There are three types of collocation within the systemic functional framework. They are ordered set collocation, activity-related collocation, and elaborative collocation [16]. The collocation itself is the cohesion that is achieved through the association of lexical items that regularly co-occur [17].

Based on the data found, there are only two types of collocation used to maintain the coherence and to promote the destinations. They are activity-based collocation and elaborative collocation. The first pattern is the pattern of activity-based collocation that points out the relation between the lexical items by using a verb to be the core of the activity.

Diagram 1. The pattern of Activity-Based Collocation

The data we found show that activity-based collocation is mostly formed by using a verb and a noun. The collocation is not only used to maintain coherence but also used to promote tourist destinations. By using activity-based collocation, a consumer or someone who visits the website and reads the tour package texts can receive the message transferred by the owner regarding the activity offered.

The next type of collocation found in the data source is elaborative collocation. This type of collocation is applied by the owner of the website to describe the tourist destinations by showing the relation among lexical items. This technique is very useful to create the image of tourist destinations. The following diagram shows the elaborative pattern applied in the tour package texts.

Diagram 2. The pattern of Elaborative Collocation

The data show that in building the image of the tourist destinations, the copywriter or the owner of the website applies elaborative collocation by using some words that occur in the same frame, although literally, they have no relation. However, by occurring together in the same frame, they build up the image and message to readers or visitors of the website. The following table shows how the tourist destinations are build up by collocation.

Table 1 Collocation Promoting Tourist Destination

No.	Tourist Destination	Activity-Based Collocation	Elaborative Collocation
1.	Ayung river	√	√
2.	Bali bird park	-	√
3.	Bantuan temple	-	√
4.	Brahmavihara-Arama	-	√
5.	Coffee plantation Bali	√	√
6.	Ijen	-	√
7.	Kemenuh butterfly park	-	√
8.	KertaGosa	-	√
9.	Kintamani	-	√
10.	Monkey forest	√	-
11.	Mount Batur	-	√
12.	Nusa Lembongan	√	√
13.	Nusa Penida	-	√
14.	Taman Ayun temple	√	√
15.	Tanah Lot	√	√
16.	TanjungBenoa	-	√
17.	Tegalalang	√	√
18.	Tegenungan waterfall	√	√
19.	TirtaGangga	-	√
20.	Turtle island TanjungBenoa	√	√
21.	Ubud	√	√
22.	Uluwatu temple	√	√

Based on the above table, the promotion of tourist destinations is built by the relation of lexical items that occur in a frame. The frame limits the discussion of the topic word, especially the tourist destination. By

building a frame using lexical items, it will guide readers or consumers to focus on the lexical topic. In addition to building information by collocation, the rule of lexical items is very important. The lexical item in a frame can build information regarding the tourist destination. This technique is employed by the copywriter or owner to promote the destinations.

IV. DISCUSSION

Collocation is another kind of lexical cohesion used to maintain coherence by using lexical items that occur in a frame. The first kind of lexical cohesion, reiteration, also plays an important role as the lexical items. However, the relation shown by the reiteration is clearer than collocation. The reiteration itself can be divided into repetition, using a synonym or near-synonym word, using superordinate, and using the general word. Although both kinds of lexical cohesion play in the level of the lexicon, the relation of lexical items in collocation is not as easy to determine as in reiteration.

As it is explained previously, there are three types of collocation within the systemic functional framework, namely ordered set collocation, activity-related collocation, and elaborative collocation [16]. The collocation is the cohesion that is achieved through the association of lexical items that regularly co-occur [17]. Collocation plays an important role in building information expressed in the text that informs the tour package offered.

Based on the data collection, there are only two types of collocation found in tour package texts. The types found are activity related to collocation and elaborative collocation. The ordered set collocation is not found in the text produced by the writer. However, both types of collocation give a clear description of how the text maintains the coherence among the lexical items.

The first type of collocation, activity-related collocation, is mostly used in the website text. This collocation produces information regarding the activity that tourist or visitor will do if the tourist or visitor choose the tour package offered. Here are some examples showing the activity related to collocation.

- 1) The *instructor* will *teach* you how to be a *skydiver* in some minutes, so don't worry about it. This is 100% safe for the *beginner*. [18]
- 2) Here we will *watch* the *Barong* Dance. [19]
- 3) TirtaGangga is perfect for a place to *takepictures* and to relax. [20]
- 4) We will invite you to *see* the *sunset* at *Tanah LotTemple*. [21]
- 5) Here you will *visit* a coffee *plantation* and see traditional coffee processing methods. [22]

In example (1), the word *instructor*, *teach*, *skydiver*, and *beginner* are the words that show the activity related to collocation. Based on this example, the pairs can be *instructor – teach – skydiver* or *instructor – teach – beginner*. Both relations are formed based on activity *teach*. In example (2), the word *watch* and the phrase *Barong dance* can be interpreted within a single frame. The relation between the lexical items here is based on activity *watch*. The example (3), (4), and (5) show the same pattern. In example (3), the word *take* and *pictures* are words that occurred in the same frame. The relation showed by both words is based on the activity *take*. Example (4) shows the word *see*, *sunset*, and phrase *Tanah Lot Temple* occur within the same frame. The activity-based collocation can be interpreted by focusing on the verb *see* as the initial of the activity. The last example shows the word *visit* and *plantation* as the pair of words that occur within the same frame. The pair is based on the activity formed by the verb *visit*.

This type of collocation shows the relation showing activity. All the lexical items were found to occur in the same frame. In addition to creating information or message informing the activity offered on the website, especially in the tour package texts, the activity-based collocation also employes verb to emphasize the information. By employing a verb that relates to a noun or some nouns in a certain frame can build single information. This type of collocation can be guidance about activity that is informed. As a tour website, this is very important and useful in conveying information.

The second type of collocation applied is elaborative collocation. This type of collocation explains that the lexical items relate to each other by occurring in the same topic. Here the topic is the only thing to define the relation of the lexical items. When they have occurred in the same topic, the lexical items can be interpreted within a frame to build the collocation between items. This type of collocation is unique if it is showed that the

items in the frame have no relation, but indeed they have a relationship within the frame based on the topic discussed. Here are the examples:

- 6) On the second day, the trip will begin in the morning to see the *sunrise* and also see *dolphins* on *Lovina* beach. [18]
- 7) After visiting Coffee Plantation Bali, the tour continued to see various *arts* and *crafts* in *Ubud* Art Village. [23]
- 8) *KertaGosa* is one of the historical *buildings* of the *Klungkung kingdom*. Formerly KertaGosa was used as a place of negotiation for the authorities and as a place of royal court. In this destination, you can see ancient buildings with Balinese *architecture*. [20]
- 9) This trip might be very memorable for you, this is because to reach the top of *Lempuyang Temple* you have to pass thousands of *stairs*. [20]
- 10) We will invite you to see the *sunset* at *Tanah Lot Temple*. [21]

Example (6) is designed to focus on Lovina. The lexical items provided to build up the lexical relation are sunrise and dolphins. Each word shows that they have no relation at all. However, they occur in the same frame, which builds up the nuance of Lovina. The next example (7) shows the word arts, crafts, and Ubud that occur in the same frame. The purpose is the same, that is to deliver a message regarding Ubud. In this case, the reader or consumer that read the text can imagine how Ubud is. Example (8) shows the relation between KertaGosa, buildings, Klungkung kingdom, and architecture. They occur in the same frame to build up the image of KertaGosa. Example (9) and (10) show the same function. The words that occurred in the same frame are used to build up the image of the tourist destination offered through the lexical relation. Lempuyang temple relates to stairs, and Tanah Lot temple relates to the word sunset.

The second type of collocation, elaborative collocation, is not easy to interpret. This type of collocation does relate to the lexical items around the topic word. In this case, the copy-writer or website owner focuses on employing this elaborative collocation to make the image of the tourist destinations. By using some lexical items that occur in a single frame. This collocation will guide and inform readers or consumers of the information regarding the destinations.

Based on the above examples and explanation, one thing that can be proved is the website owner or the copywriter wants to keep the message expressed through relation among lexical items to support and introduce tourist destinations, and of course to choose one of the tour packages offered through the website. This is not only to maintain the coherence among the parts of the language used but also to promote the service offered through the beauty of Bali and its unique culture.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis done, it can be concluded that collocation is useful to build up the image of the tourist destination offered through website text. The lexical pairs are not only formed by the lexical items relating with the activity or commonly explained as activity-based collocation but also the relationship that is formed by the lexical items which are in the same topic, it is explained as elaborative collocation. In this case, the frame is built up by the topic expressed. In implementing collocation, the copywriter or the website owner mostly focuses on the tourist destination as the topic word to build up. In this case, the lexical items deliver information regarding what readers or consumers will see or will do if they choose the package offered.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. Suarna, "Setor Rp 150 Triliun ke Pusat, Bali Ingin Minta Kontribusi," *Bali Express*, Denpasar, 13-Dec-2019.
- [2] H. Zjakic, C. Han, and X. Liu, "'Get fit!' – The use of imperatives in Australian English gym advertisements on Facebook," *Discourse, Context. Media*, vol. 16, no. 12, p. 21, 2017.

- [3] R. N. Faradhibah and N. A. Nur, "Analyzing students' difficulties in maintaining their coherence and cohesion in writing process," *ETERNAL (English, Teaching, Learn. Res. Journal)*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 183–194, 2017.
- [4] N. M. Ismail and L. Linda, "Cohesion in foreign language writing," *ETERNAL (English, Teaching, Learn. Res. Journal)*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 147–156, 2018.
- [5] I. G. N. A. Rajistha and M. D. Winaya, "Meningkatkan kesan positif pembaca teks paket perjalanan wisata melalui konjungsi," *Kulturist. J. Bhs. Budaya*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 9–15, 2020.
- [6] A. Mohseni and S. Samadian, "Analysis of Cohesion and Coherence in Writing Performance of Iranian Intermediate EFL Learners," *Issues Lang. Teach.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 213–242, 2019.
- [7] A. Al-Kharabsheh and N. Hamadeh, "Shifts of Cohesion and Coherence in the Translation of Political Speeches," *Aust. Int. Acad. Cent.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 100–112, 2017.
- [8] E. N. Najah, "Lexical cohesive devices in Nouman Ali Khan's speech," Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim, 2018.
- [9] J. Wang and Y. Zhang, "Lexical Cohesion in Research Articles," *Linguist. Lit. Stud.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2019.
- [10] N. Habibah and U. Sulisty, "The analysis of lexical cohesion in national column as found in the jakarta post newspaper," *JELT Jambi-Englih Lang. Teach.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 44–55, 2018.
- [11] G. S. Puspita, F. R. K., and D. Suprijadi, "Lexical cohesion in news article on the Jakarta post entitled 'Why full day school will not work in Indonesia,'" *Proj. Prof. J. English Educ.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 507–513, 2019.
- [12] Y. A. Rahman, "Lexical cohesion of English language nespapers in Indonesia," *J. Akrab Juara*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 161–168, 2019.
- [13] M. F. Al-Ghazalli and N. M. Majli, "A study of lexical cohesion in women's articles written by native and non-native speakers of English," *Int. J. English Lang. Linguist. Res.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–18, 2019.
- [14] Jaya and H. Marto, "Lexical cohesion in background of reserach used in undergraduated thesis: A case study in Madako university," in *English Language and Literature International Conference (ELLiC)*, 2019, pp. 343–348.
- [15] H. Alotaibi, "The role of lexical cohesion in writing quality," *Int. J. Appl. Linguist. English Lit.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 261–269, 2015.
- [16] M. Cerban, "Lexical Cohesion: Aspects of Collocation using Halliday and Hasan's Systemic model of cohesion," in *Translation Studies: Retrospective and Prospective Views*, Gelati: Gelati University Press, 2010.
- [17] M. A. K. Halliday and R. Hasan, *Cohesion in English*. London: Longman Group Ltd, 1976.
- [18] Gusti, G. Made, and K. Naya, "Activity Bali Aero Fly Station (Sky Diving)," *Gangga Bali*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ganggabali.com/packages/activities-and-adventure-tour/5cb32c002cd9c/activity-bali-aero-fly-station-sky-diving>. [Accessed: 03-Apr-2020].
- [19] Gusti, G. Made, and K. Naya, "Full Day: Barong Dance, Ubud Monkey Forest, Kintamani Volcano, Tegalalang Rice Terrace, Tirta Empul," *Gangga Bali*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ganggabali.com/packages/bali-full-day-tours/5c37f6f33ac98/full-day-barong-dance-ubud-monkey-forest-kintamani-volcano-tegalalang-rice-terrace-tirta-empul>. [Accessed: 03-Apr-2020].
- [20] Gusti, G. Made, and K. Naya, "Full Day: Kerta Gosa, Goa Lawah, Tirta Gangga, Lempuyang Temple," *Gangga Bali*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ganggabali.com/packages/bali-full-day-tours/5c191c194abb5/full-day-kerta-gosa-go-lawah-tirta-gangga-lempuyang-temple>. [Accessed: 03-Apr-2020].
- [21] Gusti, G. Made, and K. Naya, "Full Day: Kintamani Cycling, Taman Ayun Temple, Tanah Lot Sunset," *Gangga Bali*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ganggabali.com/packages/bali-full-day-tours/5bcf24628f6ca/full-day-kintamani-cycling-taman-ayun-temple-tanah-lot-sunset>. [Accessed: 03-Apr-2020].
- [22] Gusti, G. Made, and K. Naya, "Full Day: Taman Ayun Temple, Ulun Danu Temple, Jatiluwih Rice Terrace, Tanah Lot Sunset," *Gangga Bali*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ganggabali.com/packages/bali-full-day-tours/5c160c6538a55/full-day-taman-ayun-temple-ulun-danu-temple-jatiluwih-rice-terrace-tanah-lot-sunset>. [Accessed: 03-Apr-2020].
- [23] Gusti, G. Made, and K. Naya, "Full Day: Ayung River Rafting, Kintamani Volcano, Coffee Plantation Bali, Ubud Art Village," *Gangga Bali*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ganggabali.com/packages/bali-full-day-tours/5bbe9fd88ad23/full-day-ayung-river-rafting-kintamani-volcano-coffee-plantation-bali-ubud-art-village>. [Accessed: 03-Apr-2020].